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SOCIAL MEDIA AND ITS INFLUENCE ON MOTIVATION TO STUDY СОЦІАЛЬНІ МЕРЕЖІ ТА ЇХ ВПЛИВ НА МОТИВАЦІЮ ДО НАВЧАННЯ

Анотація. Сьогодні людина в середньому проводить близько більше, ніж двох годин, у соціальних мережах. Проте є речі, що стоять поза питанням часу. Ключовим є мотивація – джерело енергії до навчання. Тривожність, брак натхнення, небажання вчитися та припинення власних можливостей – все це наслідки від перегляду «мотиваційного» контенту.

Ключові слова: мотивація, ментальні розлади, вигорання, ФОМО

Abstract. Nowadays an average person spends about more than 2 hours on social media. However there are some factors which stay beyond the question of time. The most important thing is motivation – the source of force for studying. Anxiety, lack of inspiration, sadness, unwillingness to learn something new and self-destruction all of these are the consequences of consuming «motivational» content.

Keywords: motivation, mental disorders, burn-out, FOMO.

Despite the fact that social networks have been implanted in our life decades ago, the interest in studying their influence on a person's mood, motivation and willingness to be involved in comprehensive life is still slightly covered. However it is impossible to stand aside the process which can be noticed about major problems of the new generations – generation «Z» and so-called «Alpha» [3] – the people who were born at the same time with the phenomenon of social media.

Today the number of people who suffer from depression, anxiety, stress, ADHD (attention deficit hyperactivity disorder) and other psychological and mental issues has dramatically [1] increased. These factors damage all aspects of a person's life but also the most important one – motivation; and it in return harms the willingness to learn – the key ability of a human mind.

The main purpose of the research is to point out how social media influences studying process and motivation to learning; to describe its possible consequences and to motivate future development of the question.

According to a study, on average people spend about two hours on social media. And social networks provide an opportunity to share and follow others, learn something new and just consume the information a person prefers. Because of the fact that people are more likely to show the best moments of their life, browsing some networks leads to thinking and comparing the person's achievements, lifestyle and life in general with those which are highlighted.

During the last 20 year the number of mental disorders has increased [3]. A lot of people seek different kinds of counselors and specialists to deal with stress, anxiety, depression, low self-esteem, insecurity, phobia and fears. The abundance of information and opportunities cause another fear – FOMO – a fear of missing out. However being productive is also highly appreciated so the increase of burn-outs is noticed, too. So every mistake and the slightest idea of making a wrong step decreases motivation; and a lack of motivation leads to a decrease in a person's performance, especially when he\she tries to learn or study something.

Studying is a completely personal activity, nevertheless there are some trends even in this field. The content which provides up-to-date studying strategies and tips are considered to be motivational but instead a failure may cause insecurity and sadness. And an inability to fit into the proper style of studying routine may influence a curiosity and a willingness to gain some new knowledge.

The results of the research of studying works connected with the question reveal that there is a tendency to increase a level of stress and anxiety among students. Social networks as a major space for sharing information has influence on mental health in general and on a motivation to study. Fears and comparison with other people develop a pressure which grows stress and procrastination.

Despite the results, the research just sets some basic points of the question, which may be developed as the whole or separately. Because of the intense role of social media in the modern world the importance of the topic may lead to additional researches and experiments.

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